

Women Confronting Algerian Politics: *Plus ça change*

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Plus ça change, plus c'est la même chose (the more things change, the more they stay the same) captures the moment Algeria finds itself in. Many had hoped for fundamental change after the massive and peaceful Hirak movement that rocked the country from 2019 to 2021. The Hirak resulted in the ouster of President Abdelaziz Bouteflika, whose rule was plagued by corruption and ineptitude, in no small part because he was ineffective as a leader, unable to speak due to a stroke in 2013. This moment was marked by democratic hopes and aspirations; however, it was soon followed by a period of democratic stagnation, as women's political representation declined in the aftermath of the movement.

Little has changed as the country has continued under the leadership of Abdelmajid Tebboune, who has ruled the country since 2019 and has tried to distance himself from Bouteflika's policies, which included his adoption of a gender quota. In September 2024, Tebboune won 84.3% of the vote in an election with a 46.1% turnout (AP News 2019). Fraud has plagued elections, and electoral processes are opaque. The government suppresses street protests and the media, while the military continues to exert undue

influence over society. A tightly-knit circle of elite in the military and the dominant party National Liberation Front (FLN) govern the country. However, the setbacks were considerable for women in politics, even though the new 2020 constitution promised to work to promote women's political rights by "increasing their chances of access to representation in elected assemblies." The 2020 constitution even added a new provision to "protect women from all forms of violence" (Constitute Project 2020).

Extensive literature has examined the consequences of adopting gender quotas, however, there has not been much reflection on why quotas are dropped or weakened, as was the case in Algeria, where in 2012, women held 31.6% of the parliamentary seats, the highest in the Arab world (Inter-Parliamentary Union 2012). Women's representation dropped to 8% after changes in the electoral laws in 2021 (Inter-Parliamentary Union 2012). The country then moved to a proportional representation system with a gender parity requirement. This new open-list system allowed voters to select individual candidates rather than a closed list drawn up by the party. In a society where — according to

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the most recent Arab Barometer's VII wave — 76.4% of the population believe that men make better political leaders than women. The drop in women's representation was thus pre-ordained (Arab Barometer 2024). Most importantly, Article 317 of the new 2021 election law does not sanction parties for failing to meet the parity requirement on their list. Effectively, it undermined the structural support for women in politics.

Several countries like France, Italy, Egypt, Bangladesh, Nepal, and Poland adopted quotas and then like Algeria, withdrew or weakened them for a variety of reasons. However, most countries reintroduced them in another form later on. Many of the other countries in Central and East Europe had soft gender quotas prior to the decline in communism in the late 1980s and early 1990s. Some of these countries adopted formal quotas later.

Even with the quota, Algerian women remained reluctant to run for office and found it difficult to influence parliamentary or intra-party debates. They were often perceived by the public as inexperienced or unqualified and were sometimes referred to in derogatory ways as “the coiffeur [hairdresser] parliament” (Marwane 2021). There remains a large task ahead of educating the public and of providing women legislators with the tools to combat such perceptions.

While there are political setbacks, women have continued to make gains in other sectors in Algeria. The World Economic Forum noted that Algeria is one of the economies that has seen some of the largest increases in women's economic empowerment in recent years, particularly in technical and professional roles. Although, female employment rates overall are still low, women have also made gains as entrepreneurs and as traders.

Over 66.4% of university students are women, many in the STEM fields (Ghanem 2022). Algeria has the highest proportion of women engineering graduates in the world, comprising 48.5% of all graduates (Ghanem 2022). Thus, while there may be a backlash in the political arena, women are making gains in other sectors, pointing to the unevenness of women's rights in authoritarian contexts.

The decline in the percentage of women in Algeria's parliament reflects the democratic stagnation in Algeria's political order. It is driven by changes in electoral laws, inadequate enforcement of gender parity, shifts in the voting system, and enduring patriarchal attitudes. Addressing this issue requires robust legal reforms to ensure genuine enforcement of gender parity and societal efforts to challenge and change the cultural norms that hinder women's political participation. It also requires a vibrant civil society and women's movement that could press for reforms to promote women's political inclusion. As long as the regime has a stranglehold on popular participation, it will be difficult to bring about change. ♦

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